

Evaluation of Aphrodisiac Effects of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* on Sexual Behavior of *Rattus norvegicus* (Wistar Rat)

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effects of stem bark extract from *Pausinystalia yohimbe* on sexual behavior in rats. The stem bark was obtained from traditional healers in Kasuwar Magani, Amaru, Zaria City, Kaduna, Nigeria. Seventy (70) rats were divided into ten groups (seven rats per group, four males and three females) and administered the *P. yohimbe* ethanolic extract for 7 days. Phytochemical analysis of the ethanolic extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, and saponins. Sexual behavior parameters including Mount Frequency (MF), Mount Latency (ML), Intromission Frequency (IF), Intromission Latency (IL), Ejaculation Frequency (EF), and Ejaculation Latency (EL) were assessed. The ethanolic extract of *P. yohimbe*, particularly at doses of 75 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg, showed the highest aphrodisiac activity on the sexual behavioral parameters by significantly (<0.001) enhancing mount and intromission frequencies. It is recommended that *P. yohimbe* ethanolic extract should be further explored to isolate the bioactive compound that enhances the sexual behaviour parameters in wistar rats.

Keywords: Kaduna, Nigeria, *Pausinystalia yohimbe*, Sexual behavior, Wistar rats, Zaria

1.0 Introduction

Yohimbe, scientifically known as *Pausinystalia yohimbe*, is an evergreen tree whose bark is traditionally used in Africa to treat cough, fever, heart disease, and leprosy. The bark extract has also been used traditionally as an aphrodisiac, hallucinogen, and anesthetic. Now, in the West, it's often used to treat erectile dysfunction [1]. *Pausinystalia yohimbe* is a species of tree in the Rubiaceae family, native to tropical West Africa. The principal plant part used medicinally is the stem bark, which contains indole alkaloids including yohimbine as the main active compound. The alkaloid content increases with the age of the branches [1]. Yohimbe is a tree with branches in whorls at its upper end; it can grow from 9 - 30 metres tall. The straight, unbuttressed bole can be up to 50cm in diameter [2]. A popular medicinal herb in Africa, where the tree is commonly harvested from the wild for local use as a medicine and source of materials, and is

widely sold as a medicine in local markets. It has an ancient reputation in western Africa as a male aphrodisiac and mild hallucinogen, and has more recently gained scientific validation in the United States as a treatment for impotency and as a sexual stimulant [3].

Yohimbe is a monoterpene, indole alkaloid with potent pharmacological effects obtained from several biological sources [4]. It is also called quebrachine, aphrodine, corynine, and hydroaerogotocin. Indole-based pharmaceutical agents constitute a significant class of therapeutic molecules, and much progress has been made in their utilization in current therapies [5, 6]. Yohimbe has been used as a stimulant and aphrodisiac to improve erectile function.

Yohimbe is a prototypical α_2 -receptor antagonist licensed in Germany (since 1978) and Canada (since 1951) as therapy for erectile dysfunction [7]. Over several decades, it has been used as a

therapeutic agent for sexual difficulties and is a comparatively safer agent with few known adverse effects [3]. The hyperadrenergic effects of yohimbe are beneficial in various disease conditions such as erectile dysfunction, myocardial dysfunction, inflammatory disorders, and cancer [8-10]. It also has antidiuretic, anti-adrenaline, mydriatic, serotonin antagonist properties. Yohimbe combines effects of central and peripheral nervous system, including blocking of pre- and postsynaptic α -2-adrenergic receptors [11].

The studies of [3] have found that methanol extracts of *P. yohimbe* root exhibit aphrodisiac effects in male rats, increasing sexual orientation behaviors, libido, and spermatogenic activity. The extract stimulated the spermatogenic activity and accessory reproductive organs in treated rats compared to controls. The study also considered the examination of the heart of the wistar rats for the aphrodisiac effects of *P. yohimbe* roots. However, this study evaluated the stem bark extract of *P. yohimbe* on sexual parameters based on physical observations.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study area is KasuwarMagani, Amaru, located in Zaria, in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Zaria is a significant urban center known for its rich history and cultural heritage. The major occupations of the people in this area include agriculture, trading, and education, reflecting the presence of prominent educational institutions such as Ahmadu Bello University. KasuwarAmaru is situated at coordinates 11.1113° N latitude and 7.7227° E longitude, placing it in the heart of Zaria.

2.2 Sample collection and identification

The Stem bark of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* plants were purchased from traditional healers in KasuwarMagani, Amaru, Zaria City, Kaduna, Nigeria. Zaria city is located in Zaria local government area. The plants collected were then transported to the Department of Botany Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for proper identification and authentication with voucher number ABU02876.

2.3 Plant preparation and Extraction

Using a clean laboratory mortar and pestle, the stem bark of *P. yohimbe* were ground into a fine powder and air-dried at a temperature of 25°C following the procedure of Yahaya *et al.* [12]. An ethanolic extraction method was employed to obtain the crude extracts of *P. Yohimbe*. To ensure consistency in the crude extracts, the powdered sample was soaked in a mixture of distilled water and 80% ethanol. A total of 500 grams of the powder was weighed and immersed in 1000 ml of solvents for 72 hours, with occasional shaking. Initially, the mixture was filtered through gauze, and the filtrate was subsequently passed through a sterile Whatman filter (England). The resulting filtrate was then dried using a rotary evaporator at 38.5–40°C and further dried in an oven at 40°C. The dried extracts were weighed, documented, and stored in a refrigerator until needed. Prior to administration to the Wistar rats, all doses of Yohimbe extracts were diluted in distilled water.

2.4 Phytochemical analysis

The phytochemical analysis was conducted following the procedures of Yahaya *et al.* [12]

2.4.1 Test for Tannins

a. Bromine Water test

A 10 ml of bromine water was added to the 0.5 mg of desert locust oil. Decoloration of bromine water showed the presence of tannins.

b. Ferric chloride test

To test for the presence of tannins, 0.5 mg of each portion was stirred with about 10 ml of distilled water and then filtered. A few drops of 1% ferric chloride solution were added to 2 ml of the filtrate. The appearance of a blue-black, green, or blue-green precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

2.4.2 Test for Saponins

a. Frothing test

In a test tube, 5.0 ml of distilled water was combined with desert locust oil and mixed vigorously. The frothing was mixed with a few drops of olive oil and mixed vigorously and the

foam appearance showed the presence of saponins.

2.4.3 Tests for Flavonoids

a. *Shinoda Test*

Pieces of magnesium ribbon and HCl concentrated were mixed with desert locust oil after a few minutes and pink color showed the presence of flavonoid.

b. *Alkaline Reagent Test*

Exactly 2 ml of 2.0% NaOH mixture was mixed with desert locust oil; a concentrated yellow color was produced, which became colorless when we added 2 drops of diluted acid to the mixture. This result showed the presence of flavonoids.

2.4.4 Test for Carbohydrates

Molisch test

Three (3) drops of molisch reagent were added to the solution of the extract followed by the addition of conc H_2SO_4 from the side to form a lower layer. The Violet ring at the interface indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

2.4.5 Test for Alkaloid

Three(3) drops of Mayers reagent were added to the solution of the extract. Mayers reagent gives cream ppt which indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2.5 Identification and Selection of Animal Models: Wistar Rats (*Rattusnorvegicus*)

Male adult Wistar rats, weighing 30–35g and of 12 weeks of age, with female adult Wistar rats weighing 26-30g, were purchased from a standard Laboratory in Veterinary Physiology Department A.B.U, Zaria The Wistar rats werethen divided into ten groups (A–F) of seven rats each (4 males and 3 females), with each group housed separately in polypropylene cages with sawdust replaced daily. Over a period of 2 weeks (14 days), andwere provided with standard feeds and water. The treatments were as follows: Group A (Negative Control) received 0.5 ml of

distilled water, Group B (Positive Control) were treated with 5 mg/kg of Sildenafil citrate, Group C were administered 25 mg/kg of ethanolic extract, Group D received 50 mg/kg of ethanolic extract, Group E were given 75 mg/kg of ethanolic extract, and Group F were treated with 100 mg/kg of ethanolic extract. Before the experiment, the rats were given two weeks to get used to their new environment (acclimatization).

2.6 Experimental Design

The Wistar rats were placed into ten groups (A–F) of seven animals each (4 males and 3 females).Each group was kept in a separate polypropylene cage with sawdust that was replaced every day. All groups were treated as Group A (Negative Control): served as control with 0.5 ml of distilled water Group B (Positive Control): Sildenafil citrate 5mg/kg, Group C, Group D, Group E, and Group F were test groups.

2.7 Administration of oral dosesof *P. yohimbe* ethanolic extracts

Standard dosages of Yohimbe extract (Yohimbe content) were diluted with distilled water to achieve the desired concentration for accurate dosing ranging from 25 mg to 100 mg per day, for fourteen days according to the procedure [13].

2.8 Sexual Behavior Analysis

An observation cage (0.3m×0.5m×0.3m) with a mesh plate in the middle was inserted into a metal box that has a slanted mirror within.The male Wistar rat was put in the cage one hour after the treatment. The Anticipatory phase began after 10 minutes with the introduction of a sexually active female rat on the opposite side of the cage, and the Consummatory phase began after 10 minutes with the removal of the mesh plate for 30 minutes. The prospective and precopulatory activities of a male with a female were observed from the side of the cage. For a 30-minute observation period, sexual behavior metrics were directly observed [14].

The subcutaneous infusion of 17-oestradiol (15 g/kg) to the pre-determined oestrous cycled female rats 48 hours before they were matched in cages with the male rats was used to assess the oestrous cycles of the female rats (sexual cycles). The same group of female rats received

progesterone (500 g/rat) dissolved in 30% Tween 80 40 hours later [15].

After receiving their daily doses at intervals of three days, the male and female rats were observed for sexual behavioral activity. Male rats were removed and replaced with new ones if they could not have intromission within the first 15 minutes. Male sexual parameters were recorded during observation.

- Mount Latency (ML), time from the introduction of the female until the first mount.
- Intromission Latency (IL) is the time from the introduction of the female until the first intromission.
- Ejaculation Latency (EL) is the time from the first intromission until ejaculation.
- Mount Frequency (MF), is the number of mounts in a series.
- Intromission Frequency (IF), is the number of intromissions in a series.
- Ejaculation frequency (EF), is the number of times there was expulsion of semen by males after vaginal penetration characterized by rhythmic contraction of the posterior abdomen.

2.8 Data Analysis

Data obtained was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The data was statistically analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc test least significant difference (LSD) to determine the significance between effects resulting from exposure to the test and the control at a significant level of $p < 0.05$. Table and figure were used for data presentation and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used for the analysis.

Table 1: Phytochemicals detected in *Pausinystalia yohimbe*

Constituents	Aqueous Extract	Ethanollic Extract
Alkaloids	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Carbohydrates	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	+	+

KEY: + = present

3.0 Results and Discussion

The development of plant-based drugs has been pivotal in *in vivo* research, significantly enhancing reproductive health by providing natural and safe alternatives to synthetic drugs. Across diverse cultures worldwide, plants have been utilized as natural and safe sources of medicines to address the persistent decline in sexual behavior. This practice highlights the crucial role of plant-based compounds in enhancing reproductive health through natural interventions [15]. Recent research has underscored the efficacy of various plant-based products in augmenting male sexual function, underscoring the imperative to explore further botanical resources to combat the increasing prevalence of sexual dysfunction globally [16].

3.1 Phytochemical analysis

The aqueous extracts of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* were subjected to qualitative phytochemical screening for the detection of phytochemical constituents like glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids carbohydrates, saponins proteins, and tannins. The results revealed the presence of glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids carbohydrates, saponins proteins, and tannins. Tannins are attributed to the sexual stimulation activity of most medicinal plants because of the presence of potential bioactive compounds causing increasing testosterone produced naturally and improving male sexual behavior [17]. A study by [18] evaluated the aphrodisiac properties of extracts from *Microdesmis keayana* roots, rich in alkaloids, which significantly improved various sexual behaviors in Wistar rats, and concluded that alkaloids play a critical role in enhancing male sexual behavior by influencing neuroendocrine pathways and improving erectile function.

3.2 Sexual Behaviour Analysis

Table 2 presents the effects of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* ethanolic extracts on various aspects of sexual behavior in male Wistar rats, measured on Day 1. The parameters assessed include Mount Frequency (MF), Mount Latency (ML), Intromission Frequency (IF), Intromission Latency (IL), Ejaculation Frequency (EF), and Ejaculation Latency (EL). In the treatment

groups, Group A was the control group treated with distilled water and Group B with Sildenafil Citrate which is the standard control group while Groups C-F were treated with various doses of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* extract.

For the Mount Frequency (MF) parameters, Group A was observed with 0.66, while Group B is 1.45 which is significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher than Group A and Groups C-F were observed with 0.00 ± 0.00 MF which shows no manifest, and no noticeable effect on Mount frequency for the Intromission Frequency (IF) Group A was observed with 1.35 while Group B with 1.81 IF value that was slightly higher than Group A, and Groups C-F: 0.00 values with no intromission behavior observed. The Intromission Latency (IL) in seconds was observed with Group A at 762.00, and Group B at 140.00 with lower latency, indicating quicker intromission compared to Group A and Groups C-F: 0.00 with no intromission behavior observed. For the Ejaculation Frequency (EF), Group A was recorded with 1.35 while Group B with 1.72 with a significantly higher frequency than Group A

and Group C: 0.00 with no ejaculation behavior observed. The Ejaculation Latency (EL) in seconds, Group A is observed with 0.68 EL value, Group B with 1.22 which is a significantly higher latency compared to Group A and Group C: 0.00 where observed to be inactive (Table 2)

On day 1 of this study, *Pausinystalia yohimbe* extracts were observed with no impact on all the sexual behavior parameters (MF, ML, IF, IL, EF, and EL) in Wistar rats. This is in contrast with the work of Oyewole et al. [19] which states that Mount Frequency (MF) and Intromission Frequency (IF) are useful indices of vigor, libido, and potency while the number of mounts (MF) reflect sexual motivation from day 1. An increase in the number of intromission (IF) shows the efficiency of erection, penile orientation, and the ease by which ejaculatory reflexes are activated. Therefore, the increase in MF and IF following the administration of aqueous extract of *Parquetina nigrescens* root at all doses in all days of observation suggests enhanced libido.

Table 2: Effect of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* Extract on Male Wistar Rats' Sexual Behaviour on Day 1

Treatment Groups	Mount Frequency (MF) No	Mount Latency (ML) in secs	Intromission frequency (IF) No	Intromission Latency (IL) secs	Ejaculation Frequency (EF)	Ejaculation Latency (in Sec)
Group A (Distil water)	0.66 ± 0.02^b	6.00 ± 0.58^a	1.35 ± 0.01	762.00 ± 4.16^a	1.35 ± 0.01^b	0.68 ± 0.02^b
Group B (SC)	1.45 ± 0.02^a	0.72 ± 0.01^b	1.81 ± 0.01	140.00 ± 0.58^b	1.72 ± 0.01^a	1.22 ± 0.01^a
Group C (25mg/kg) Ethanolic	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c
Group D (50mg/kg) Ethanolic	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c
Group E (75mg/kg) Ethanolic	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c
Group F (100mg/kg) Ethanolic	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c	0.00 ± 0.00^c
Total	0.21 ± 0.08	0.67 ± 0.34	0.32 ± 0.12	90.20 ± 42.30	0.31 ± 0.12	0.19 ± 0.07
p Value	$< 0.001^*$	$< 0.001^*$	$< 0.001^*$	$< 0.001^*$	$< 0.001^*$	$< 0.001^*$

* - Means along columns with different superscript(s) are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to DMRT. The sexual behavioural parameters (SBP) were highly significant ($p < 0.05$) across the treatment groups

Table 3 presents the Aphrodisiac effects of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* ethanolic extract on the sexual behavior of male Wistar rats on day 7. For MF, the highest value (8.60 ± 0.06) was observed in rats treated with sildenafil citrate in Group B,

followed by Group F (8.40 ± 0.06) treated with 100mg/kg ethanolic extract of *P.yohimbe* then Group E (7.30 ± 0.17) treated with 75mg/kg ethanolic extract. The least MF (3.40 ± 0.06) was observed in Group C, treated with 25 mg/kg of

ethanolic extracts, so it increases in a dose-dependent manner.

A statistically significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was observed among the different concentrations of extracts. ML was highest in Group C (228.00 ± 1.73 seconds) treated with 25 mg/kg extract followed by Group F (227.00 ± 2.31 seconds) treated with 100mg/kg of ethanolic extract while the least was recorded in Group B (145.60 ± 1.10) treated with Sildenafil Citrate. IF value was highest in Group E (3.20 ± 0.06) treated with 75mg/kg of ethanolic extract, while the least was observed in Group A (1.50 ± 0.17) distilled water. A significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was noticed with the groups treated with different extracts on Wistar sexual behavior. IL was highest in Group A treated with distilled water (765.00 ± 2.89 seconds), followed by Group C (298.00 ± 1.73) while the least IL was observed in Group E (240.00 ± 1.73) treated with 75mg/kg of ethanolic extract. For EF, the highest value was observed in Group F (2.40 ± 0.12) administered with 100 mg/kg of aqueous extract while the least ejaculation frequency (1.20 ± 0.00) was recorded in Group C exposed to 25 mg/kg of aqueous extract. Ejaculation latency (EL) was highest in Group E (467 ± 2.31 seconds) treated with 75 mg/kg of ethanolic extract, while the least latency was recorded in Group A (263.40 ± 0.17 seconds) treated with distilled water.

On day 7, the ethanolic extract at higher doses (75mg/kg and 100mg/kg) exhibited the most potent improvement in sexual behavior parameters in the rats, particularly in mount (MF) and intromission frequency (IF), with the best results observed at 75mg/kg. MF and IF are useful indices of vigor, libido, and potency. While the number of mounts (MF) reflects sexual motivation, an increase in the number of intromissions (IF) shows the efficiency of erection, penile orientation, and the ease by which ejaculatory reflexes are activated [14]. In another study of Y the administration of *Fadogia agrestis* stem extract demonstrated a significant increase in intromission frequency, further supporting the notion that the extract facilitates penile erection [20] also recent research on the ethanol extract of *Ganoderma lucidum* has highlighted the effectiveness of plant-based products in enhancing male sexual function. It has shown that it significantly increases the number of mounts and intromission frequency in male rats,

indicating enhanced sexual desire and adequate penile erection, respectively [21]. This suggests the potential use of such extracts in treating erectile dysfunction. The increase in IF of the male rats induced by the extract in this study suggests that the penile erection was activated. Therefore, extract of *P.yohimbe* may increase potency by allowing or sustaining erection. Plant activities on penile erection have been attributed to the various phytochemicals, like the alkaloids and saponins, in plants which have erogenic properties in vasodilation of the blood vessels and consequent erection [22].

Mount latency (ML) and intromission latency (IL) are indicators of sexual motivation. ML and IL are inversely proportional to sexual motivation. Mount latency time which is an indicator of physical exhaustion during sexual act. For this study ML and IL increases significantly across ethanolic extracts of *P.yohimbe*. Increased ML and IL could indicate anti-androgenic properties of the plant extracts, which might be due to the presence of phytochemicals that inhibit androgen receptors or reduce testosterone levels. This could have implications for the treatment of androgen-dependent disorders, such as acne, hirsutism, or prostate cancer [23]. Also, the increased latency times could suggest anxiolytic and sedative properties of the plant extracts. This could be beneficial for the treatment of anxiety disorders, insomnia, or other conditions where sedation is necessary [23]. Furthermore, changes in ML and IL could have implications for reproductive function in rats. For example, increased ML and IL might indicate reduced fertility or altered mating behaviors, which could be relevant for understanding the effects of plant extracts on reproductive health [24]. Lastly, the observed effects on ML and IL could lead to the development of new therapeutic strategies for treating various conditions, such as anxiety disorders, androgen-dependent disorders, or reproductive issues [23]. In contrast, [19, 22] and [21] oppose this study, stating that the decrease in the mount and intromission latencies observed at all doses of the extract in this study might imply stimulation of sexual motivation and libido. It may also be an indication of enhanced sexual appetitive behavior in male rats. All these further support the sexual function-improving effect of the extract at these doses. The prolonged ejaculation latency by the 50, 100 and 150mg/kg body of the extract is an indication that

copulatory performance in the animals was enhanced. It may also imply prolongation in the duration of coitus [18]. The significant increase in ejaculation latency (EL) in all doses of *P. Yohimbe* extracts suggests that the extracts and standard drug prolonged the duration of coitus, which is an indicator of an increase in sexual motivation [22]. Similarly observed that the

prolonged ejaculation latency of the extract of *M. angustifolia* at 30 and 300 mg/kg is an indication that copulatory performance in the animals was enhanced. Similar findings have been reported by Guohua et al. [23] on the extracts of *Allium tuberosum* and [26] on the extracts of *Moringaoleifera*.

Table 3: Shows the day 7 evaluation of the effects of *Pausinystalia yohimb* ethanolic extract on male Wistar rat sexual behavior.

Treatment Groups	Mount Frequency (MF) No	Mount Latency (ML) (secs)	Intromission frequency (IF) No	Intromission Latency (IL) (secs)	Ejaculation Frequency (EF)	Ejaculation Latency (Sec)
Group A (Distil water)	3.20±0.06 ^f	200.50±0.17 ^b	1.50±0.17 ^f	765.00±2.89 ^a	1.32±0.02 ^{cd}	263.40±0.17 ^b
Group B (SC)	8.60±0.06 ^a	145.60±1.10 ^c	1.95±0.02 ^c	298.80±1.85 ^c	2.20±0.06 ^{ab}	351.20±0.35 ^f
Group C (25mg/kg) Ethanolic	3.40±0.06 ^f	228.00±1.73 ^a	1.20±0.06 ^f	298.00±1.73 ^c	1.60±0.17 ^c	295.00±2.31 ^c
Group D (50mg/kg) Ethanolic	4.60±0.12 ^c	191.00±1.73 ^c	2.60±0.06 ^c	270.00±1.73 ^e	2.30±0.17 ^{ab}	370.00±1.15 ^c
Group E (75mg/kg) Ethanolic	7.30±0.17 ^b	180.00±2.31 ^c	3.20±0.06 ^a	240.00±1.73 ^f	2.36±0.05 ^{ab}	467.00±2.31 ^a
Group F (100mg/kg) Ethanolic	8.40±0.06 ^a	227.00±2.31 ^a	2.80±0.17 ^{bc}	280.00±2.31 ^d	2.40±0.12 ^{ab}	386.00±1.73 ^c
Total	5.04±0.38	194.91±4.92	2.30±0.12	337.58±27.55	2.03±0.09	360.26±11.76
p Value	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*

* - Means along columns with different superscript(s) are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to DMRT. The sexual behavioral parameters (SBP) were highly significant ($p < 0.05$) across the treatment groups.

Table 4 presents the Aphrodisiac effects of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* ethanolic extract on the sexual behavior of male Wistar rats on day 14. A highly significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was observed in the sexual behavioral parameters. The mount frequency was highest in Group B with 8.60 ± 0.17 , followed by Group E with 7.30 ± 0.06 and Group D with 4.60 ± 0.06 while the least mount frequency was in Group A with 3.30 ± 0.17 . Mount latency was highest in Group C at 228.00 ± 0.58 seconds, followed by Group E at 180.00 ± 0.58 seconds. The intromission frequency number of 3.30 ± 0.12 was the highest and it was observed in Group E, the least intromission frequency number was recorded in Group A with 1.50 ± 0.12 this is inline with the work of [27] after the administration of aqueous extracts of *M. angustifolia* at doses of 30 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg significantly increased MF and IF in male Wistar rats. The highest MF was recorded in rats receiving 300 mg/kg, comparable to those treated with Viagra. The study indicated that the duration of treatment did not significantly affect MF or IF,

suggesting the extract's immediate effects on sexual motivation and erection efficiency. In contrast with another study which reported that the aqueous extract of *Cnestis ferruginea* reduced both MF and EF while increasing ML and IL. This suggests that while some plant extracts enhance sexual behavior, others may have inhibitory effects, highlighting the complexity of phytochemical interactions on sexual function [28]. Increased MF is often associated with heightened sexual motivation, while IF reflects the efficiency of erection and the activation of ejaculatory reflexes. The studies emphasize that the increase in these parameters following plant extract administration indicates improved sexual vigor and libido. For instance, the extracts were found to contain phytochemicals like alkaloids and saponins, which are known to promote vasodilation and enhance erectile function [23]. Intromission latency was highest in Group A with 432.10 ± 0.81 seconds, followed by Group B with 300.50 ± 0.98 seconds while Group F had the least intromission latency of 250.00 ± 0.58

seconds. Ejaculation frequency was highest in Group D with 2.50 ± 0.12 , followed by 2.40 ± 0.17 observed in Groups B and F, while the least ejaculation frequency was observed in Group A with 1.40 ± 0.12 . Ejaculation latency of

470.00 ± 1.73 seconds was the highest and was observed in Group E, followed by B with an ejaculation latency of 389.30 ± 9.76 seconds respectively while the least ejaculation latency of 263.20 ± 1.62 was observed in Group A. (Table 4).

Table 4 shows the day 14 evaluation of the effects of ethanolic extract of *Yohimbeon* male Wistar rats sexual behavior.

Treatment Groups	Mount Frequency (MF) (No)	Mount Latency (ML) (secs)	Intromission on frequency (IF) (No)	Intromission Latency (IL) (secs)	Ejaculation Frequency (EF)	Ejaculation Latency (Sec)
Group A (Distil water)	3.30 ± 0.17^f	204.20 ± 0.29^e	1.50 ± 0.12^d	432.10 ± 0.81^a	1.40 ± 0.12^d	263.20 ± 1.62^h
Group B (SC)	8.60 ± 0.17^a	145.60 ± 0.52^h	2.00 ± 0.12^c	300.50 ± 0.98^c	2.40 ± 0.17^{ab}	389.30 ± 9.76^c
Group C (25mg/kg) Ethanolic	3.40 ± 0.17^f	272.00 ± 0.58^a	2.10 ± 0.17^c	288.00 ± 1.73^d	1.60 ± 0.17^{cd}	296.00 ± 1.15^f
Group D (50mg/kg) Ethanolic	4.60 ± 0.06^c	189.00 ± 1.15^e	2.60 ± 0.12^b	270.00 ± 2.89^e	2.50 ± 0.12^a	375.00 ± 0.58^d
Group E (75mg/kg) Ethanolic	7.30 ± 0.06^b	170.00 ± 1.15^f	3.20 ± 0.06^a	240.00 ± 1.73^e	2.30 ± 0.17^{ab}	470.00 ± 1.73^a
Group F (100mg/kg) Ethanolic	4.40 ± 0.12^{cd}	230.00 ± 0.58^b	2.80 ± 0.17^b	250.00 ± 0.58^f	2.40 ± 0.17^{ab}	387.00 ± 1.15^c
Total	4.65 ± 0.32	197.78 ± 6.63	2.43 ± 0.11	300.16 ± 11.60	2.03 ± 0.09	364.95 ± 12.13
p Value	$<0.001^*$	$<0.001^*$	$<0.001^*$	$<0.001^*$	$<0.001^*$	$<0.001^*$

* - Means along columns with different superscript(s) are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to DMRT. The sexual behavioral parameters (SBP) were highly significant ($p < 0.05$) across the treatment groups.

4.0 Conclusions

The ethanolic extract of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* at higher doses (75mg/kg and 100mg/kg) exhibited the highest aphrodisiac activity in sexual behavior parameters of Wistar rats, particularly in mount and intromission frequencies.

5.0 Recommendations

Further studies required to determine the optimal dose of both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* that can maximize sexual behavioral parameters without causing adverse effects.

It is recommended to investigate the long-term effects of *Pausinystalia yohimbe* extracts on sexual behavior to assess any potential side effects or benefits over extended periods.

It is also recommended that *P. yohimbe* ethanolic extract should be further explored to isolate the

bioactive compound that enhances the sexual behaviour parameters in wistar rats

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